

Creation of a Forest Garden

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Market garden beds interspersed with rows of fruit trees at La Ferme des Rufaux

In 2012, the *Ferme des Rufaux* planted 200 high and half-stemmed pome fruit trees on a 2-hectare plot of its market-garden farm. The farm purchased 12 old varieties of grafted apple trees, aged between 2 and 5 years, from a retired nurseryman at a price of €3 each. The trees are planted 8 meters apart in all directions. As soon as they were planted, 4 market garden beds were set up between each row, facing east-west to limit the amount of shade cast on the vegetables. Small fruits (raspberries, blackcurrants, redcurrants) and rhubarb are grown on the rows of fruit trees, with tarpaulins to limit weed growth. This system is both ecological (120 species of birds recorded over a year), ergonomic (providing shade in summer), and economical (diversification of farm products). Plowing in the first two years allowed the trees' root system to grow deep, avoiding water competition with the crops. The vegetables benefit from irrigation at planting and, if necessary, from additional watering, supplemented by natural rainfall. The fruit trees are maintained annually by a professional pruner. The initial goblet shape pruning proved inadequate, as it made it difficult for the tractor to pass through. Trellising was preferred, but this led to alternating years of high yields (8 tonnes in 2020) and low yields (4 tonnes in 2021). Drawing on its experience, the *Ferme des Rufaux* advises reducing the orchard's planting density to one row in two to make handling easier. If possible, its pruner recommends doing the grafting on-site to save money, reduce health risks, and allow the trees to develop a structure adapted to local conditions and prevailing winds. The farm also recommends diversifying species within the same area to limit the spread of potential diseases.

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